

CEEC-TACS & Medicta2019

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

Editors:

Andrei Rotaru

Stefano Vecchio Cipriotti

**5th Central and Eastern European Conference on
Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry
&
14th Mediterranean Conference on
Calorimetry and Thermal Analysis**

**27-30 August 2019
Roma, Italy**

Book of abstracts of the 5th Central and Eastern European Conference on Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry (CEEC-TAC5) and 14th Mediterranean Conference on Calorimetry and Thermal Analysis (Medicta2019).

5th Central and Eastern European Conference on Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry (CEEC-TAC5) and
14th Mediterranean Conference on Calorimetry and Thermal Analysis (Medicta2019).

27-30 August 2019

Roma

Italy

Editors:

Andrei Rotaru, Stefano Vecchio Cipriotti

Copyright:

© 2019 Central and Eastern European Committee for Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry (CEEC-TAC)

Publisher: Central and Eastern European Committee for Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry (CEEC-TAC)

Publishing House: *Academica Greifswald, Germany*

ISBN 978-3-940237-59-0

Organizers

**The 5th Central and Eastern European Conference
on Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry**

&

**The 14th Mediterranean Conference on
Calorimetry and Thermal Analysis**

CEEC-TAC5 & Medicta2019

27-30 August 2019 – Roma, Italy

is organized by the:

**Central and Eastern European Committee for
Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry (CEEC-TAC),**

Italian Association for Calorimetry and Thermal Analysis (AICAT),

**Interdivisional Group of Calorimetry and Thermal Analysis (GICAT)
of the Italian Society of Chemistry,**

**Sapienza University of Rome (SUR), Dipartimento di Scienze di Base
e Applicate per l'Ingegneria Sapienza (SBAI),**

University of Craiova (UCV),

National Institute for Laser, Plasma and Radiation Physics (INFLPR),

**Institute of Physical Chemistry "Ilie G. Murgulescu" (ICF)
of the Romanian Academy**

Organizing Committees

Chairmen: Stefano Vecchio Cipriotti (Italy) & Andrei Rotaru (Romania)

Vice-Chairmen: Ignazio Blanco (Italy) & Matko Erceg (Croatia)

International Organizing Committee

Pierre Brodard (Switzerland)

Swiss Association for Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry

Petru Budrugaec (Romania)

Commission for Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry of the Romanian Academy

Konstantinos Chrissafis (Greece)

Hellenic Society of Thermal Analysis

Eric Dantras (France)

French Association for Calorimetry and Thermal Analysis

Fabio Faraguna (Croatia)

Committee for Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry of the
Croatian Society of Chemical Engineers

Konstantin S. Gavrichev (Russia)

National Committee of Russia on Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry

Janos Kristof (Hungary)

Thermoanalytical Branch of the Hungarian Chemical Society

Giuseppe Lazzara (Italy)

Interdivisional Group of Calorimetry and Thermal Analysis of the
Italian Society of Chemistry

Vesa-Pekka Lehto (Finland)

Finnish Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry Association

Vilma Petkova (Bulgaria)

Bulgarian Society of Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry

Oleg Petuhov (Moldova)

Society for Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry of Moldova

Krzysztof Pielichowski (Poland)

Polish Society of Calorimetry and Thermal Analysis

Peter Simon (Slovakia)

Slovak Group for Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry

Petra Sulcova (Czech Republic)

Czech Working Group for Thermal Analysis

Juan Josep Sunyol (Spain)

Spanish Group of Calorimetry and Thermal Analysis

Dirk Walter (Germany)

Association for Thermal Analysis Germany

Members of the International Organizing Committee

Dimitris Achilias (Greece)	Jiri Kucerik (Czech Rep.)	Martin Palou (Slovakia)
Isabelle Beurroies (France)	Dragan Manasijevic (Serbia)	Nicolas Sbirrazzuoli (France)
Mira Bissengaliyeva (Kazakhstan)	Daumantas Matulis (Lithuania)	Bedrich Smetana (Czech Rep.)
Romana Cerc-Korosec (Slovenia)	Nina Obradovic (Serbia)	Muhamed Suceska (Croatia)
Eduard Coropceanu (Moldova)	Rodica Olar (Romania)	Irena Szczygiel (Poland)
Saeda Didaoui (Algeria)	Nilgun Ozpazan (Turkey)	Maria R. Tine (Italy)
Jordi Farjas (Spain)	Stefano Materazzi (Italy)	Alexander Toikka (Russia)
Loic Favergeon (France)	Thomas Maskow (Germany)	Hanna Trebacz (Poland)
Hans Flandorfer (Austria)	Alfred Menyhard (Hungary)	Andres Trikkel (Estonia)
Vera L.S. Freitas (Portugal)	Stefana Milioto (Italy)	Mikhail Varfolomeev (Russia)
Maya Guncheva (Bulgaria)	Rosa Nomen (Spain)	Titus Vlase (Romania)
Dijana Jelic (BiH)	Vlad T. Popa (Romania)	Arturas Zalga (Lithuania)

Executive Organizing Committee

Anca Badoi	Marius Criveanu	Francesco Marra	Bogdan Sava
Liana-Sanda Baltes	Liviu Costiuc	Ioan Milosan	Luciana Sciascia
Federico Barrino	Olesea Cuzan-Munteanu	Marcela Milosan	Maria Stoicanescu
Mihaela Bojan	Alessandro Dell'Era	Anca Moanta	Dumitru Ureche
Lucica Boroica	Claudiu Dobrinescu	Sorin Munteanu	Natalia Terenti
Giuseppe Cavallaro	Gabriel Dumitru	Ana Ostasevschi	Cristian Tigae
Dorin Catana	Florin Firu	Aura Precupas	Alina Tigae
Diana Chisca	Viorina Gorincioi	Filippo Parisi	Athanasios Tiliakos
Andrea Ciccioioli	Vasile Lozovan	Roberta Risoluti	Elisabetta Tranquillo
Ionela Criveanu	Iulia Lungu	Natalia Rotari	Aliona Vitu

*President of the conference: **Teodoro Valente**
(Deputy Rector for Research Innovation and Technology
Transfer of Sapienza Univ. of Rome)*

Honorary Committee

*Honorary Chair: **Giuseppe Arena** (Italy)
(President of the Italian Society for Calorimetry and Thermal Analysis, AICAT)*

Lorezno Abate	Tudor Lupascu	Crisan Popescu
Branka Andricic	Jan Majling	Maria Ribeiro da Silva
Jerzy Blazejowski	Bruno Marongiu	Jean Rouquerol
Attilio Cesaro	Erwin Marti	Leszek Rycerz
Nicolae Doca	Slavko Mentus	Christoph Schick
Michael Feist	Andrzej Mianowski	Alberto Schiraldi
J. Ruben Garcia	Dragica Minic	Jaroslav Sestak
Jean-Pierre Grolier	Eric Mittemeijer	Raimundas Siauciunas
Katarina Gyoryova	Dumitru Oancea	Judit Simon
Vladimir Ivanov	Barbara Pacewska	Vicenc Torra
Mustafa V. Kok	Henryk Piekarski	Cornelia Vasile
Gyorgy Liptay	Yoncho Pelovski	Serge Walter
Marek Liska	Jose L. Perez-Rodriguez	Maria Zaharescu
Vladimir A. Logvinenko	Polycarpos Pissis	Irina Zvereva

Scientific Committee

Chairs of the Scientific Committee:

Michelina Catauro (*Italy*), **Concetta Giancola** (*Italy*), **Jiri Malek** (*Czech Rep.*),
Luis A. Perez-Maqueda (*Spain*) & **Sergey Verevkin** (*Germany*)

K. Achgar (Morocco)	A. Gorska (Poland)	B. Pagano (Italy)
G. Aldica (Romania)	A. Grajcar (Poland)	J. Pekez (Serbia)
M. Antonijevic (United Kingdom)	T. Holjevac Grguric (Croatia)	A. Perejon (Spain)
D. Ambrosini (Italy)	I. Iglesias (Spain)	L. Petraccone (Italy)
H. Arslan (Turkey)	D. Ivanov (France)	R. Pietrzak (Poland)
J. Avsec (Slovenia)	R.M. Ion (Romania)	S. Porcedda (Italy)
M. Badea (Romania)	Z. Jacimovic (Montenegro)	H. Pruchnik (Poland)
V. Bakic (Serbia)	D. Jozic (Croatia)	S.L. Randzio (Poland)
L. Balanovic (Serbia)	M. Jozwiak (Poland)	P. Relkin (France)
G. Bruni (Italy)	K. Katoh (Japan)	I. Riposan (Romania)
L.G. Bujoreanu (Romania)	O.A. Kirichenko (Russia)	I. Ristic (Serbia)
R. Bulanek (Czech Rep.)	W.P.C. de Klerk (the Netherlands)	D. Rosu (Romania)
R. Burriel (Spain)	Z. Kozisek (Czech Rep.)	P. Rotaru (Romania)
D. Cangialosi (Spain)	M. Krunks (Estonia)	P.E. Sanchez-Jimenez (Spain)
A.M. Cardinale (Italy)	S. Kurajica (Croatia)	P.J. Sanchez Soto (Spain)
N. Celan Korosin (Slovenia)	D. Lorinczy (Hungary)	L.M.N.B. Santos (Portugal)
S. Chidiac (Canada)	R. Lyszczyk (Poland)	M. Scampicchio (Italy)
E.L. Charsley (United Kingdom)	K. Ludzik (Poland)	C. Sgarlata (Italy)
I. Chicinas (Romania)	B. Maaten (Estonia)	J. Shanelova (Czech Rep.)
Z. Cibulkova (Slovakia)	T. Machedon-Pisu (Romania)	P. Siler (Czech Rep.)
W. Ciesielski (Poland)	D. Majda (Poland)	A.F. Sousa (Portugal)
C. Corcione (Italy)	T.M.R. Maria (Portugal)	O. Stefanescu (Romania)
A. Cucos (Romania)	A. Melchior (Italy)	N. Stipanelov Vrandecic (Croatia)
T. Dambrauskas (Lithuania)	A. Michnik (Poland)	G. Strbac (Serbia)
M. Dinescu (Romania)	C. Milanese (Italy)	N. Strbac (Serbia)
Z. Drzazga (Poland)	A. Miyake (Japan)	D. Streltsov (Russia)
E. Drozd (Poland)	M.J.M. Monte (Portugal)	M. Sumar Ristic (Serbia)
C. Duce (Italy)	J.C. Moreno Pirajan (Colombia)	B. Szczygiel (Poland)
M. Dudek (Poland)	R. Moustafine (Russia)	I.M. Szilagyi (Hungary)
A. Duran (Spain)	X. Moya (United Kingdom)	E. Tarani (Greece)
M.B. Fernandez Alfonso (Spain)	G. Nounesis (Greece)	M. Tierean (Romania)
M. Fernandez Garcia (Spain)	L. Novotny (Slovakia)	M. Tolazzi (Italy)
D. Fessas (Italy)	E. Omanovic-Miklicanin (Bosnia & Herzegovina)	G. Vlase (Romania)
C. Fleaca (Romania)	E. Ostrowska-Ligeza (Poland)	M. Voncina (Slovenia)
N. Gelfond (Russia)	C. Pacurariu (Romania)	M. Wesolowski (Poland)
A. Georgiev (Bulgaria)	P. Pasierb (Poland)	P. Yuan (China)
E. Govorcin Bajsic (Croatia)		L. Zelenina (Russia)
		Z. Zovko Brodarac (Croatia)

General Information

The joint event “5th Central and Eastern European Conference on Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry (CEEC-TAC5) & 14th Mediterranean Conference on Calorimetry and Thermal Analysis (Medicta2019)” has gathered **372 registered participants** from **38 countries** and of **6 continents**, presenting a total number of **451 scientific works**. Of those, 4 are Plenary Lectures (**PL**), 3 are Award Plenary Lectures (**APL**), 16 are Invited Lectures (**IL**), 4 Parallel Sessions of Oral Presentations – 108 contributions (**OP**) & 3 Sessions of Poster Presentation – 320 contributions (**PS**). Each session of oral presentations is comprised of 27 works, poster session 1 and 2 include 106 works each, while poster session 3 has 108 works.

An important task of CEEC-TAC5 & Medicta2019 is the continuation of 2 distinctive directions that the first conference follows, with 2 Workshops (**WS**) introducing the subjects:

- 1) *Advanced Functional Materials*;
- 2) *Kinetics and Lifetime Prediction of Materials (KLTPM)*.

Plenary Lectures

- *Kestutis Baltakys* (Kaunas University of Technology, Lithuania)
- *Dimitrios N. Bikiaris* (Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece)
- *Nobuyoshi Koga* (Hiroshima University, Japan)
- *Janos Kristof* (University of Pannonia, Hungary)
- *Vahur Oja* (Tallinn University of Technology, Estonia)
- *Crisan Popescu* (KAO European Research Laboratory, Germany)
- *Henrik Rudolph* (Applied Surface Science, Elsevier, the Netherlands)

Invited Lectures

- *Arnon Chaipanich* (Chiang Mai University, Thailand)
- *Svetlana Danilova-Tretiak* (A.V. Luikov Heat&Mass Transfer Institute, Belarus)
- *Ahmed El-Sabbagh* (Ain Shams University, Egypt)
- *Nathanael Guigo* (University of Cote d'Azur, France)
- *Tiit Kaljuvee* (Tallinn University of Technology, Estonia)
- *Dana Luca Motoc* (Transilvania University of Brasov, Romania)
- *Cheila G. Mothe* (Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil)
- *Wojciech Marczak* (Jan Dlugosz University in Czestochowa, Poland)
- *Jonjaua Ranogajec* (University of Novi Sad, Serbia)
- *Iulian Riposan* (University Politehnica of Bucharest, Romania)
- *Adriana Saccone* (University of Genoa, Italy)
- *Pablo Taboada* (University of Santiago de Compostela, Spain)
- *Paul S. Thomas* (University of Technology Sydney, Australia)
- *Ranjit K. Verma* (Patna University, India)
- *Anna Vkydalova* (Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava, Slovakia)
- *Kseniya Zherikova* (Nikolaev Institute of Inorganic Chemistry, Russian Federation)

Characterization of weld metal in welded microalloyed steel J55 made using a rutile electrode with a flux-cored wire core

**Mihailo MRDAK¹, Jasmina PEKEZ², Nikola BAJIĆ³, Marko Rakin⁴,
Darko VELJIĆ², Zoran RADOSAVLJEVIĆ⁵, Mića Djurdjev²**

¹Research and Development Center, IMTEL Communications a.d., Boulevard Mihaila Pupina 165b, Belgrade, Serbia

²University of Novi Sad, Technical Faculty „Mihajlo Pupin“, Đure Đakovića bb, Zrenjanin, Serbia

³ IHIS Techno-experts d.o.o. - Research and Development Center, Batajnički drum 23, Belgrade, Serbia

⁴ Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy, , University of Belgrade, Karnegijeva 4, Belgrade Serbia

⁵Research and Development institute Lola Ltd., Kneza Visislava 70A, Belgrade, Serbia

The development and production of welding electrodes with enhanced properties represents complex research that requires changes in certain technological phases of making the core and coating [1-3]. Improving the properties of the electrodes by changing the properties of the steel core is possible by replacing solid wire with alloyed flux-cored wire.

The possibility of use of flux-cored wire for making the electrode core requires primarily that the thickness of the steel shell is sufficient to enable the preparation of the rod of a required diameter and length with straight ends, to which the coating can evenly be applied by continuous pressing.

This paper presents the results of tests of mechanical properties (yield strength, tensile strength and toughness) at various temperatures and microstructure of welded joints of microalloyed high strength (HSLA) steels J55 (according to API Spec 5L) implemented using new quality coated electrodes.

The mastered quality of the coated rutile electrode has a core of flux-cored wire alloyed with Ni and Mo. The main objective of this research is to define the justification of replacing the solid wire electrode core with flux-cored wire.

[1] M. Mrdak, N. Bajić, M. Rakin, S. Stojadinović, D. Veljić, , Inter. J. of Engineering, XIII (2015), pp.75-78.

[2] M. Mrdak¹, N. Bajić², M. Rakin³, S. Stojadinović⁴, J. Pekez⁴, Inter. Conf. Industrial Engineering and Environmental Protection, 2014, pp.119-122.

[3] M. Mrdak, N. Bajić, D. Veljić, M. Rakin, S. Stojadinovic, Z. Karastojkovic, Acta Technica Corviniensis - Bulletin of Engineering, Tome IX[2016], Fascicule 1[January-March], ISSN:2067-3809, pp.20-22

Publishing house

ISBN 978-3-940237-59-0

Copyright

© Central and Eastern European Committee for Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry
2019

Not for sale!
Pas à vendre!
Non in vendita.
Nicht zum Verkauf!
Nu este de vânzare!
Nem értékesítésre szánt!
није на продају
Nije na prodaju
Ni za prodajo
Nie je na predaj!
Není na prodej!
Nie na sprzedaż!
Ne pardavimui!